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The Specifics of the Elective “School of Leadership” Using Repositories of Online Resources

Objective. Modern online library resources play an important role in the organisation and conduct of the School of Leadership elective. The purpose of this study is to consider the peculiarities of conducting the elective “School of Leadership” for applicants using online resource repositories. **Methods.** A comprehensive approach to the study of the problem led to the use of such theoretical research methods as the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical, psychological and sociological literature to identify the specifics of leadership and leadership competence, the analysis of repositories of online resources, synthesis, comparison, generalization of various scientific approaches to the basic concepts of the study and determination of the specifics of the organization and conducting the elective “School of leadership”. **Results.** The work clarifies the essence of the concepts “leadership competence”, “elective”, “elective class”, discloses the peculiarities of organization and conduct, main tasks, content modules, organizational and pedagogical conditions of the elective “School of leadership”. The work describes the knowledge and skills that students will be able to improve and develop thanks to a properly planned and organized elective using the resources of online repositories. Particular attention is paid to the features of ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of the elective for the formation of students’ leadership competence and the content of the elective “School of leadership”, which depends on the achievement of the set goal, aims and tasks for the development of student-leaders. **Conclusions.** The main results that were obtained within the framework of this scientific research should be considered the substantiation of the concept of “elective” and the description of the specifics of the organization and the conducting of the elective “School of leadership” for students. The results of this scientific research, as well as the conclusions formulated on their basis, are of practical value for scientists, teachers of educational institutions, psychologists and other specialists who are engaged in the study of leadership problems and the formation of leadership competence and the search for effective methods, means and forms of work for the development of applicants’ leadership potential.

Keywords: leadership; leader; leadership competence; leadership potential; elective; libraries; repository; online resources; applicant

Introduction

In the modern conditions of the development of society, technology and science, there is a need for erudite, qualified, effective and goal-oriented workers-leaders who have pronounced organizational competences, an inner desire for social activity, who are able to unite people around them to achieve their goals, are ready to long and intense work in order to create favorable conditions for further development. Moreover, it is not enough for modern specialists to possess only developed professional knowledge, skills and qualities, but also it is necessary to have developed leadership competencies and qualities that enable them to quickly adapt to environmental changes, find the right solutions in various difficult situations, be self-confident, persistent and determined. In view of this, the development of applicant’ leadership competence is a necessary requirement and need of modern times. One of the ways to develop the students’ leadership competence is electives. In the modern scientific literature, special attention is paid to the issues of formation of leadership abilities, qualities and competencies of applicants, more in a theoretical plan than in a practical one. The practical aspects of leadership development remain outside the attention of researchers, in particular, consideration of the specifics of conducting

electives, trainings, special courses, lectures, etc. as effective means of forming students' leadership competence.

Nelia Lebid claims that leadership competence is a set of personal characteristics of a human being and his professional abilities, which under certain external and internal conditions ensure his influence on the results of the work of other people who are subordinate to him (Lebid, 2016, p. 45).

Liudmyla V. Lishtaba emphasizes that leadership competencies are skills and abilities that provide an opportunity to influence others (Lishtaba, 2016, p. 120).

Diana A. Volkivska (2014) believes that leadership competence consists in the ability to predict, i.e. notice the slightest signs of changes, emerging trends, as well as quickly react to changes and show flexibility in order to quickly respond to new demands of the environment, to align, i.e. to reconcile one's own values and needs with values and the needs of other people in order to form a team and its effective and coordinated activity and to act, that is, to create conditions for achieving the goal and persistently move towards it.

As for the means of forming leadership competence, the researcher O.D. Pavlyuk pays special attention to the training and believes that the purpose of the training is to expand students' ideas about leadership as a way of organizing and managing a small group, to develop leadership qualities of students and to activate their personal leadership potential in the process of developing self-management and group management skills. According to the researcher, the main tasks of the training are students' acquisition of knowledge about the nature and essence of leadership and leadership qualities, their identification of their own leadership potential and individual leadership style, development of students' leadership qualities and individual leadership style, assessment of students' leadership qualities using psychodiagnostic methods during training, development of students' skills in regulating their emotional state, self-analysis skills and working in a group (Pavlyuk, 2019, p. 29).

Tetiana O. Kononova emphasizes that a special place in the field of leadership formation is occupied by electives and optional courses aimed at forming a general idea of the essence of leadership, the importance of leadership competencies in professional activity, its components and functions. According to the researcher, it is necessary to use active forms and methods of learning in optional classes, including business games, lectures-discussions, brain-rings, analysis of specific situations, etc., because such methods and forms of work give the greatest effect (Kononova, 2014, p. 170).

Mykhailo M. Fitzula (2006) claims that it is important to develop such students' leadership competencies in elective classes as the ability to make decisions and avoid unfavorable situations or, on the contrary, master the methods of psychological influence. It should also be taken into account that the elective can consist not only of students of the same group, but also of students from parallel groups, different courses and faculties. This opens up opportunities for leadership, competition, and opportunities for multifaceted communication and collaboration. Therefore, in elective classes, it is important to have the opportunity to freely exchange ideas, joint practical and independent tasks, experiments or projects.

Nataliia Logvinenko notes that optional classes not only form students' interest and their positive attitude to the educational process, but also encourage students to open up, show their "self", develop leadership potential, get rid of categorical forms of thinking, open their consciousness to new ideas and perspectives, develop the ability to apply leadership skills and abilities in practice, use effective methods of getting out of stressful, conflict and crisis situations, use tactics of reasonable persuasion, increase team effectiveness, organize training within the organization, manage emotional intelligence. In addition, elective classes teach students to constantly move forward, make decisions in difficult situations, see perspectives, achieve goals

and solve set tasks, establish cooperative relationships, adapt to changes, interact with bearers of other leadership styles during decision-making, their implementation, form a team, manage personnel and changes, etc. (Logvinenko, 2011, p. 45).

The intrinsic value in the educational process have online resources. Students can use materials about leadership gained either form educational institutions or platforms supported by businesses. Efforts to establish communication with professional organizations, for example The International Leadership Association, provide the students with an access to valuable toolkits and open new opportunities for future career.

As we can see, the problem of leadership has been and continues to be one of the most researched topics among many scientists, because society needs leaders and organizers who possess the skills of effective personnel management, are capable of empathy, and are ready to carry out activities based on personally oriented interaction.

Aim. Today, many libraries around the world and in Ukraine in particular provide a variety of online services. Each university library is represented on the web, where any user can get acquainted with the services it provides. These include an electronic catalog of the library's collections, online search, ordering and delivery of literature, video lessons and lectures, own full-text databases, use of social networks, and an e-archive of full-text documents posted in open access repositories. About 100 institutional repositories of Ukrainian universities are represented in the Webometrics ranking "Transparent Ranking: Institutional Repositories from Google Scholar" (Eurosvita, 2023). These resources contribute to the development of leadership competencies and the acquisition of leadership, communication, teamwork, public, personal and other skills necessary for career development. Therefore, these resources should be actively used during the School of Leadership elective.

The purpose of this study is to consider the peculiarities of conducting the elective "School of Leadership" for applicants using online resource repositories. It is worth noting that modern library online resources play an important role in organizing and conducting the elective "School of Leadership". Today, many libraries in Ukraine provide a variety of online services.

The objectives of this article are as follows: 1) analysis of scientific approaches to the problem of determining the essence of leadership competence and the elective as an effective means of its formation; 2) identifying the specifics of the organization and holding the elective "School of leadership" for applicants using repositories of online resources.

Methods

The basis of the methodological approach in this work is a complex systematic study, which is based on a qualitative combination of theoretical research methods. In particular, analysis, synthesis, generalization, interpretation, abstraction, as well as descriptive, comparative, comparison method, and comparative-historical method were applied for a detailed examination of the essence of elective classes and features of conducting the elective "School of leadership" for applicants namely by means of repositories of online resources.

Results

In the conditions of the intensive European integration process in Ukraine, the problem of forming a strong, creative, leadership personality becomes extremely important, because any link in the social sector needs such a specialist who is able to unite people around him to achieve the set goals, to create favorable conditions for further development. Accordingly, any educational institution today faces the task of developing the student as a leader and professional in his field,

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teaching him to make decisions on his own, developing his leadership abilities and independence (Bespartochna & Skrebkova, 2022, p. 18). However, at the current stage, a large number of students have hidden leadership potential, but they do not reveal it for various reasons. As a result, there is a decrease in interest in other people, there is a lack of interaction, cooperation and partnership skills, and a lack of motivation. For this reason, it is necessary to develop and implement in practice a training system that prepares leaders (Yemchuk & Chubrei, 2022, p. 123).

We strongly believe that one of the effective means of forming students' leadership competence is elective classes, in particular the elective "School of leadership". First of all, it is worth noting that an elective (lat. facultatis – optional, from lat. facultas – opportunity, ability) is an educational course, a subject that is optional for students of an educational institution to attend in order to expand and deepen their knowledge. Elective classes are one of the forms of organizing the educational process, which are held outside of classes for students to deepen their knowledge of various subjects, which depends on the requests, inclinations and abilities of students (Logvinenko, 2011, p. 46). The elective is based on the principle of voluntariness, but despite this, attendance at the elective is mandatory for enrolled participants.

It is worth noting that the main tasks of electives are the following:

- development of abilities and personal qualities of students;
- development of leadership qualities and abilities of applicants;
- deepening and expanding professional knowledge of students;
- development of creative abilities, creativity, independence and organization of students;
- formation of students' interest in science and self-improvement;
- development of organizational skills – that is, the student must be able to organize personal educational and professional activities;
- formation of stress resistance and the ability to achieve set goals.

For high performance and efficiency of electives, it is necessary to organize electives only taking into account the following principles:

1) the principle is aimed at the freedom and independence of the student, the student's right to his own choice and self-expression, in such classes the student should feel free and aware of himself as a future specialist-leader. This is a kind of democracy, which involves the rule of trust, politeness, freedom of thought and free expression of students' own assumptions in classes;

2) the principle of revealing personal factors – creative abilities, talents, leadership qualities, that is, the student must reveal himself as a person to the full extent;

3) the principle of expanding the spheres of communication – communication in a new team, exchange of ideas, information, the opportunity to analyze the work of other students, correct, give advice and even give an assessment. After all, communication promotes the exchange of additional educational information, broadens the horizons of students, enriches their emotional and sensory sphere during contact with other people.

As for the elective "School of leadership", it is aimed at forming a general understanding of the essence of leadership, the importance of leadership competencies in professional activity, their components and functions. The task of this elective course is to deepen students' knowledge about themselves, their psychological characteristics, their awareness of their actions and thoughts, strengthening positive personality qualities, acquiring skills of adequate behavior in certain social situations, practicing organizational and communication skills that characterize the personality of a group leader, as well as forming a strategy of leaders' actions to transfer acquired knowledge and skills to the entire student body.

The content of the elective involves the presence of several content modules. Such modules may include: leadership and power; similarity and difference; structure and dynamics of

leadership; leader's legitimacy; signs of a potential leader; the means by which a special socio-psychological role or "myth" of the leader is created; psychological foundations of leadership; the meaning of human existence and professional activity from the standpoint of philosophical and historical culture; moral foundations of professional activity; formation of special skills of influence on communication partners; ways of influencing people, etc.

The specified content modules provide consideration of a wide range of issues, among which the main ones are: the difference between leadership and management; the essence of the concepts "leadership", "leadership competence", "leader"; leadership as a qualitatively new level of management; leadership assessment criteria; leadership and charisma; types of leadership; basic theories of leadership and types of leaders; the main roles, functions, qualities and skills of a leader; portrait of a modern leader; world leaders whose work inspires youth, etc.

Thus, during elective classes, students must acquire knowledge about the characteristics of leadership, power and management; differences between a leader and a manager; basic theories of leadership; basic requirements for leadership qualities of a manager; variety of leadership styles; effective communication algorithm; features of conducting business negotiations; basics of conflict and stress management.

For example, the first class of the elective "School of leadership" should be organized in the form of an interactive lecture and using video materials that reveal the essence and content of the leadership phenomenon, the historical origins of leadership, theories and concepts of leadership; division, types and criteria of leadership; basic principles of leader behavior. In groups, you can discuss the following important questions: What is leadership for you? Is it an innate ability or can it be developed? Is it easy to be a leader? Why do we need leadership? Other classes should be made practical, in which the participants of the elective will learn about the basics of leadership and will work on developing and improving the main components of leadership competence, performing various exercises and tasks. In addition, in practical classes and in the process of independent work, students should learn to form requirements for leadership qualities; distinguish leadership from management; analyze leadership styles; to reveal one's own leadership potential; conduct an analysis of resources and limitations for building leadership potential; use techniques, methods of acquiring authority in the team; use technologies to strengthen leadership positions in emotionally tense, problematic and conflict situations; to have self-analysis skills; have an active communication style, be able to establish and maintain partnership relations; take into account the consequences of management decisions and actions from the standpoint of social responsibility; to design the organizational structure of the institution, to distribute powers and responsibilities based on their delegation; analyze and design interpersonal, group and organizational communications.

As you can see, the elective program covers the concepts of the social and psychological content of leadership, power, authority, charisma, group dynamics, problems of the effectiveness of group activity and group cohesion, features of effective management, group management, use of decision-making mechanisms, management of conflicts and conflict situations. At the elective "Leadership School" it is necessary to use active methods and forms of work, for example, business games, discussions, round tables, seminars-workshops, competitions, webinars and verbal methods, such as a story, a conversation, an explanation, a narrative, a discussion, a polemic, a discussion, etc. (Bratko, 2022, p. 71).

An unrestricted access to repository of online materials and information about leadership is provided by Oxford University Press and the International Graduate School of Leadership (the Philippines). In 2022, OUP published over 22,000 open access articles, and retains the second highest mean lifetime citation rate for OA articles among major competitors, demonstrating the reach, quality, and impact of our publishing (www.academic.oup.com). IGSL Library has an

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ebook lending platform offering content across all subject areas with a growing collection of more than 200 000 titles from major publishers worldwide. The largest B2B content and free ebook offers for professionals can be found on TradePub.com, Leadr. The members of TradePub enjoy free unlimited access to free research, white papers, reports, case studies, magazines, and eBooks. The Manager's Toolkit offered by Leader contains popular ebook's and pdf resources that are full of practical, action-orientred steps managers can take to lead their teams (www.insights.leadr.com).

The International Leadership Association is a global community of leaders, educators and leadership resedearchers that advance the study and practice of leadership. By becoming a member of ILA students can be equipped with resources that will propel them towards new heights of excellence. ILA's book series offer the best contemporary thinking about leadership from diverse range of scholars, educators and practitioners (Building Leadership Bridges). They enjoy free access to numerous journals, blogs, videos pertaining to the study and practice of leadership (www.ilaglobalnetwrk.otg).

Though students are unlilely to be enrolled on training programs offered by some companies. But they can use some mobile applications/ For example, in 2012 Vital Learning released a mobile application, Vital Learning Pocket Coach for Supervisors, launching a new trend in delivering and consuming training content (www.vital-learning.com/about-us).

It is worth noting, that libraries also play an important role in building students' leadership competence by providing access to knowledge, information, and resources that can contribute to the development of students as future leaders. Libraries give access to information, they contain extensive collections of books, journals, scholarly articles, electronic resources and other sources of information. This provides students with access to current knowledge and research in a variety of fields, which is the foundation for developing their expertise and leadership skills. Libraries help students develop research skills, including locating information, evaluating sources, analyzing data and writing literature reviews. These skills are critical for leaders as they must make informed decisions and manage projects.

Furthermore, libraries usually provide quiet spaces for study and research, as well as spaces for group work. This fosters self-management and teamwork skills, which are important for future leaders. Librarians can assist students in finding the right resources, teaching information literacy, and even advising on research. This helps develop communication and counselling skills that are important for leaders. Modern libraries also provide access to digital resources and technology to help students develop skills related to data processing and the latest information technology.

For example, the Scientific Library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technology (USUST) is a modern library aimed at meeting the information needs of the university community in educational, research, pedagogical and managerial practice by providing resources and services and creating information products (<https://library.ust.edu.ua/uk>).

The library finds ways to provide quality service to its readers. The issue of the lack of modern Ukrainian-language educational publications and the provision of quality distance learning is relevant today. This can be solved with the help of Open Educational Resources (OER). For this purpose, the scientific library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technology (USUCT) conducts extensive educational work to encourage other universities to join this movement. The website of the scientific library presents a series of video lectures for Ukrainian universities "Open Education and Open Educational Resources: Importance for Ukrainian Higher Education" (Scientific Library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies, 2023). The library's website provides access to the open online course "Using Open Educational Resources in Teaching" from the Politecnico di Milano (Italy) https://www.pok.polimi.it/courses?search_query=OER101/. Over the past two years, together

with the authors-teachers of USUCT, the library staff has been actively involved in the preparation of textbooks and manuals using the Creative Commons license. The use of online services and information provided by the USUCT Scientific Library will be useful for future leaders and teachers who organize the elective “School of leadership”.

Within the framework of conducting the elective “School of leadership” it is necessary to first of all provide such organizational and pedagogical conditions under which the process of forming the leadership competence of applicants would take place most effectively. Such conditions include the following:

the need to implement the interaction of state and public institutions in the formation of socially significant personal qualities of students;

1) creation of a complete system of effective communication in the activities of teaching staff and students of education in an educational institution;

2) ensuring the inclusion of students in a real system of social relations within public organizations and study groups of an educational institution;

3) correspondence of the internal position to the system of pedagogical influences;

4) creation of a positive spiritual and moral climate in the educational institution in general and in each student group, an atmosphere of mutual assistance, responsibility for the performance of professional and official duties;

5) emotional adaptation of students in an educational institution, confidence in their abilities and the importance of their chosen professional path.

Adhering to the above-mentioned organizational and pedagogical conditions, participants of the elective “School of leadership” get the opportunity to improve:

- leadership skills to defend one’s point of view and position;
- mastery of planning and organizing one’s activities;
- the art of working independently and in a team, interacting as a whole;
- organizational skills,
- the ability to assess and use one’s own potential and the potential of the team.

Moreover, having created the above conditions, participants of elective classes will be able to:

- identify the characteristics of the leader’s behavior;
- work on using their leadership qualities and abilities;
- learn about their role in the team, effective interaction with other team members;
- learn about their strengths and weaknesses in order to use them when solving various situations;

• try out a variety of behavioral strategies and understand their own work and leadership style;

- realize one’s hidden possibilities and one’s own potential;
- become a leader who inspires others to action thanks to his own example;
- work on self-improvement and develop their uniqueness.

Results and Discussion

The task of any educational institution is to promote the development of students’ leadership competence and their creative potential, self-realization of the individual, to form readiness for personal self-improvement and self-development. In view of this, the problem of developing a purposeful system of work for the development and activation of the leadership potential of young people is particularly acute today. As it was mentioned, one of the effective

means of developing students' leadership competence is elective classes. The conducted research allows us to state that the organization and implementation of the elective "School of leadership" is a complex task that requires thorough preparation, strong knowledge of the teacher and taking into account a number of features.

The effectiveness of elective classes and the formation of leadership competence on them largely depends on the teacher. Important in this aspect is the degree of competence of the teacher himself, the ability to rationally apply and combine forms and methods of education. In this case, the creative abilities and individual approach of the teacher occupy almost the first place. That is why experienced teachers should conduct and organize electives. It is even advisable to invite teachers from other educational institutions to conduct electives.

According to the researcher N. Logvinenko (2011), in the conditions of elective classes, a necessary condition is correctly selected ways of pedagogical influence on the formation and development of cognitive interests, both professional and general. And therefore, the leading role of the teacher in the formation of leadership competence in elective classes is undeniable. Actually, individualization and methodical support depend on the professionalism and training of the teacher, on which the effectiveness of independent work of students depends. The teacher acts not only as a leader, but also as an instructor, consultant, organizer, who is faced with the task of interest, motivation and encouraging students to take action (p. 46).

In addition, it was found that available repositories of online resources with unlimited access aid learning providing up-to-date and cutting edge materials. A wide range of topics, issues and cases curated by academic, educational institutions and businesses give an extensive insight into leadership. Moreover, "School of leadership" should teach a young person to demonstrate and develop basic leadership qualities and competently use their leadership potential; to improve the skills and abilities of possessing charismatic influence, principles of flexibility, basic technologies of self-motivation and management.

The results obtained within the scope of this scientific research, as well as the conclusions formulated on their basis, can be used as an effective scientific base for further study of the problem of leadership competence formation in elective classes in modern educational institutions. In addition, the materials of this article can be used by scientists who deal with the problems of studying the specifics of conducting the elective "School of leadership" for students, teachers and various other specialists who study issues related to the phenomenon of leadership, the formation of leadership competence and the development of leadership potential of applicants.

The prospect of further research of this issue is, first of all, the implementation of a deeper study of electives as a means of forming the leadership competence of student youth in a modern educational institution, as well as an experimental verification of the effectiveness of the elective "School of leadership".

Limitations. The study includes some methodological limitations and limitations of the researcher. To the methodological limitation belong lack of available and reliable data and lack of prior research studies on the topic. To the limitations of the researcher belong longitudinal effects, cultural and other type of bias.

Conclusions

The carried out scientific study of the features of conducting the elective "School of leadership" for applicants provides grounds for formulating the following conclusions.

It was determined that the elective "School of leadership" is aimed at forming a general understanding of the essence of leadership, the importance of leadership competencies in professional activity, their components and functions. Its main task is to deepen the knowledge of

students about leadership and leadership competence, to stimulate creative and social activity and initiative of young people, to form students' responsibility for the changes taking place in their lives and in their further successful professional career. Having in-depth online resources about leadership at students' finger-tips equips them with requisite expertise and fosters prospective qualification in administration, management, governorship, etc.

The process of organizing and conducting the elective "School of leadership" should be aimed at creating favorable conditions for the self-realization of each student, revealing his or her leadership qualities and leadership potential, activating and improving the individual experience of each young person, making him or her aware of his or her own characteristics and resources, helping everyone to set individual goals in education and social life to improve themselves as a leader and their environment. It is also important to use all available resources to effectively organize and conduct this elective. One of these resources is online library resources that provide access to a large amount of diverse information that can be used to successfully organize the School of Leadership elective and develop students' leadership competencies (Kolesnykova, 2023; Kolesnykova, Gorbova, & Shcherbatiuk, 2022).

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Специфіка роботи факультативу «Школа лідерства» з використанням репозиторіїв онлайн-ресурсів

Мета. Сучасні бібліотечні онлайн-ресурси відіграють важливу роль в організації та проведенні факультативу "Школа лідерства". Мета дослідження полягає у розгляді особливостей проведення факультативу «Школа лідерства» для здобувачів освіти з використанням репозиторіїв онлайн-ресурсів. **Методика.** Комплексний підхід до дослідження проблеми зумовив використання таких теоретичних методів дослідження, як аналіз філософської, педагогічної, психологічної та соціологічної літератури для виявлення специфіки лідерства та лідерської компетентності, синтез, порівняння, узагальнення різних наукових підходів до основних концепцій вивчення та визначення специфіки організації та проведення факультативу «Школа лідерства». **Результати.** У роботі з'ясовано сутність понять «лідерська компетентність», «факультатив»,

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«факультативне заняття», розкрито особливості організації та проведення, основні завдання, змістові модулі, організаційно-педагогічні умови факультативу «Школа лідерства». У роботі описано знання та вміння, які здобувачі освіти зможуть вдосконалити та розвинути завдяки правильно спланованому та організованому факультативу. Особливу увагу приділено особливостям забезпечення ефективності факультативу для формування лідерської компетентності студентів та змісту факультативу «Школа лідерства», від якого залежить досягнення поставленої мети, цілей і завдань для розвитку студентів-лідерів. **Висновки.** Основними результатами, які були отримані в рамках даного наукового дослідження, слід вважати обґрунтування поняття «факультатив» та характеристику специфіки організації та проведення факультативу «Школа лідерства» для студентів. Результати цього наукового дослідження, а також сформульовані на їх основі висновки мають практичне значення для науковців, викладачів освітніх закладів, психологів та інших спеціалістів, які займаються дослідженням проблем лідерства й формування лідерської компетентності та пошуком ефективних методів, засобів і форм роботи для розвитку лідерського потенціалу здобувачів освіти.

Ключові слова: лідерство; лідер; лідерська компетентність; лідерський потенціал; факультатив; бібліотеки; репозиторій; онлайн-ресурси; абітурієнт

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